

Prospective Study of Complications of Acute Pancreatitis (Local and Systemic) and its ManagementRajiv Khurana¹, Jitender Sirohiya², Sumit Kumar³¹Assistant Professor, Department of Surgery, Shaheed Hasan Khan Mewati Government Medical College, Nuh, Haryana, India²Assistant Professor, Department of Anesthesia, Shaheed Hasan Khan Mewati Government Medical College, Nuh, Haryana, India³Assistant Professor, Department of Anesthesia, Shaheed Hasan Khan Mewati Government Medical College, Nuh, Haryana, India

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Abstract:**Objective:** To study various presentations, investigations and complications of acute pancreatitis and their management.**Methods:** prospective study of complications of acute pancreatitis (local and systemic) and its management. The study randomly enrolled the patients of acute pancreatitis as determined by clinical, biochemical, and radiological diagnosis. The following parameters were considered complicated pancreatitis. Development of systemic complications and development of local complications. In follow-up all the discharged patients were advised to come for follow up weekly for a period of 3 months.**Results:** The study includes a total of 50 patients of complicated pancreatitis. 42 male and 8 female. The peak incidence in male is 4th decade in life and in female 3rd decade in life. Alcohol accounts 80% total cases where as gall stone contributes 16%. Most systemic complication were managed in general wards except few patients in ICU those were associated with septicemia and ARDS. Systemic complication were managed with supportive and conservative management. Local complications were managed conservatively and with operative procedures. Pseudocyst <6 cm were managed with regular USG abdomen follow up 75% resolved Pseudocyst >6 cm undergone operative procedure. All the patients with pancreatic necrosis were kept in ICU. Pancreatic abscess were managed by USG/CT guided aspiration.**Conclusion:** Most systemic complication were managed in general wards except few patients in ICU those were associated with septicemia and ARDS. Systemic complication were managed with supportive and conservative management. Local complications were managed conservatively and with operative procedures. In general mortality from local complications was 13% mortality from systemic complication was 4%.**Keywords:** Systemic Complication, Septicemia, ARDS, Supportive And Conservative Management, Severe Acute Pancreatitis, Necrosectomy, Percutaneous Drainage.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Acute pancreatitis is one of the most common differential diagnoses of acute abdomen especially in alcoholic and biliary calculi. Patients of acute pancreatitis presents with acute onset of abdominal pain which radiates to back, associated with raised serum amylase and lipase levels. The burden of AP is only expected to increase over time. Despite recent advances in medicine, pancreatitis continues to be associated with a substantial morbidity and mortality. The most common cause of AP is gallstones, followed closely by alcohol use. The diagnosis of pancreatitis is established with any two of three following criteria: [1] Abdominal pain consistent with that of AP; [2] Serum amylase and/or lipase greater than three times the upper limit of normal; and [3] Characteristics findings seen in

cross-sectional abdominal imaging. Multiple criteria and scoring systems have been established for assessing severity of AP. The cornerstones of management include aggressive intravenous hydration, appropriate nutrition and pain management.

Acute pancreatitis patients should be evaluated thoroughly clinically, blood investigation and radiological as this condition is associated with many complications both systemic and local. Early diagnosis is essential to manage the complications and decrease mortality and morbidity. Most systemic complications of acute pancreatitis are hypovolemia and systemic infection where as local complications are pseudocyst/necrosis. Serum lipase

is elevated in all patients 2-3 times and >5 times in pancreatic necrosis. Investigations of complicated pancreatitis requires hematological and biochemical investigations and chest x-ray to identify systemic complications whereas USG/CT recognizes local complications.

Patients with local complications should be referred to specialist tertiary centres to guide further management, which may include drainage and/or necrosectomy. The impact of acute pancreatitis can be devastating, so prevention or reduction of the risk of recurrence and progression to chronic pancreatitis with an increased risk of pancreas cancer requires proactive management that should be long term for some patients.

Materials and Methods

The study was conducted on 50 patients of Acute Pancreatitis admitted in MMIMSR, Mullana, Ambala in a period of two years. The study was prospective study of complications of acute pancreatitis (local and systemic) and its management. The study randomly enrolled the patients of acute pancreatitis as determined by clinical, biochemical, and radiological diagnosis.

Inclusion Criteria

- Age- All adults
- Patients who will present with acute abdominal pain associated with raised serum lipase/ amylase level
- Patients who will present with acute abdominal pain associated with swollen pancreatic parenchyma detected by USG/ CT scan.

Exclusion Criteria

- Traumatic pancreatitis
- Pancreatitis in pregnancy
- Post ERCP in cases of gall stone pancreatitis

All the patients were evaluated thoroughly at the time of admission and subsequently to find out associated local/ systemic complications. Blood samples for laboratory studies will be taken on admission and after 48 hrs. Ultrasonography and CECT will be done to find out the complications. The arterial oxygen tension value were measured

during spontaneous respiration on room air. The total volume of fluid requirement was calculated to maintain haemodynamic stability as following parameters-

1. CVP of 8-12 mmHg
2. BP of mean arterial pressure >60mmHg.
3. Urine output at least 1ml/Kg/min.

Fluid sequestration was estimated by subtracting measured urinary and nasogastric output from the volume of intravenous fluid administered. Initial conservative management consists of nasogastric suction, intravenous administration of fluid, antibiotics and supportive care in hospital. An indwelling urinary catheter was placed in most patients to allow close monitoring of urinary output and a CVP catheter was also frequently introduced. Most of the systemic complications were managed by conservative and supportive care in ICU.

The following parameters were considered complicated pancreatitis-

Development of systemic complications-

1. Shock (systolic BP < 90mmHg)
2. Pulmonary insufficiency $PO_2 < 60$ mmHg or less require ventilation or O_2 therapy.
3. Renal failure (output < 400ml/24 hr), serum creatinine > 2mg%.
4. Severe metabolic disturbance (serum calcium 7.5mg/dl or less).

Development of local complications-

1. Pancreatic pseudocyst
2. Pancreatic abscess
3. Pancreatic necrosis
4. Pancreatic ascites, pleural effusion, fistula
5. Follow- up
6. All the discharged patients were advised to come for follow up weekly for a period of 3 months. Out of 50 patients, 27 did not have any complaints, 8 patients had recurrent abdominal pain and 11 did not come for follow up.

Observation Chart

A total of 50 patients of acute pancreatitis associated with complications were entered in the study group. All had an admission of acute pancreatitis and satisfied the inclusion criteria.

Table 1 sex distribution and types of complications

Sex (n = 50)	Local complications	Systemic complications	Total	Percentage (%)
Male	17	25	42	84
Female	6	2	8	16
Total	23	27	50	100

Table 2: Clinical presentation

Clinical features	No of patients (n= 50)	Percentage %
Pain abdomen	50	100
Vomiting	41	82
Distension	21	42
Fever	9	18
Jaundice	4	8
Ileus	8	16
Mass abdomen	4	8

Pain abdomen was the presenting complaint in almost all of the 50 patients. Other clinical feature includes vomiting in 41, distension in 21, fever in 9, ileus in 8, jaundice in 4 and mass abdomen in 4. Cullen's sign and grey turner sign was seen in 6 cases associated with severe necrotizing pancreatitis.

Table 3: Etiology of pancreatitis

Etiology	No of patients (n=50)	Percentage %
H/O alcohol	40	80
Biliary calculi	8	16
Drug induced	2	4
Total	50	100

The history of alcohol consumption and its likely hood of being the etiological factor was seen in 40 patients. While gallstones were implicated in 8 patients and 2 patients developed drug induced pancreatitis.

Table 4: Local complications

Local Complications	n= 23
Pseudocyst	7
Necrosis	8*
Abscess	4**
Ascites	2
Ascites+ Pleural effusion	2

Table 5: Outcome of pancreatic pseudocyst

S. No	Size of cyst	No of cases	Management	Recovery
1	<6 cm	4	USG follow up	(75%)
2	>6 cm	3	1 case of PCD and 2 cases of internal drainage (Cystogastrostomy)	All
Total		7		

Table 6: Outcome of pancreatic necrosis

S. No	Nature of necrosis	Admission	Management	Duration in hospital (in weeks)	Outcome
1	Sterile	ICU	Conservative	3	Recovered
2	Sterile	ICU	Conservative	3.3	Recovered
3	Sterile	ICU	Conservative	4	Died
4	Sterile	ICU	Conservative	2.5	Recovered
5	Sterile	ICU	Conservative	3.2	Recovered
6	Infected	ICU	Surgical	4	Recovered
7	Infected	ICU	Surgical	4.5	Recovered
8	Infected	ICU	Surgical	5	Died

Table 7: Management of pancreatic abscess

S. No	Location	No of abscess	Nature of content	Organism	Procedure	Duration in weeks	Outcome
1	Body	Single	Purulent	Gram negative	CT guided drainage	3	Recovered
2	Tail	Single	Purulent	Gram negative, anaerobes	USG guided drainage	2.5	Recovered
3	Tail	Single	Purulent	Mixed	USG guided drainage	2.5	Recovered
4	Body & tail	Multiple	Purulent/necrotic	Mixed	Open drainage	1.2	Died

Table 8: Systemic complications

Systemic Complications	n = 27
Hypovolemia	10*
Hypovolemia with ARF	4
Septicemia	3**
Septicemia with ARDS	2
Hypocalcemia	8
Total	27

*Two patients of hypovolemia also had necrosis

**One patient of septicemia also had abscess

Table 9: Management of systemic complications

Management	No of patients	Percentage %
General ward	22	81
ICU without ventilator	3	11
ICU with ventilator	2	8
Total	27	

50 patients of acute pancreatitis with complications were evaluated clinically, biochemically and radiologically. Out of 50 patients 23 were found to have local complications and 27 were found to have systemic complications

Table 10: Mortality from systemic complications

Complication	Mortality
Hypovolemia	0
Hypovolemia with ARF	0
Septicemia	0
Septicemia with ARDS	1
Hypocalcemia	0

Out of 27 patients with systemic complications, one patient expired because of septicemia with ARDS. Patients with infected necrosis were managed surgically (surgical debridement, necrosectomy and close drain).

Table 11: Outcome of complications

S. No	Outcome	No. of Patients
1	Cured	38
2	Morbidity	8
3	Death	4

Out of 50 patients, 38 patients were cured, Morbidity was seen in 8 patients and 4 patients expired.

Results

- The study includes a total of 50 patients of complicated pancreatitis. 42 male and 8 female. The peak incidence in male is 4th decade in life and in female 3rd decade in life. Alcohol accounts 80% total cases where as gall stone contributes 16%.

- Serum lipase raise in 2-3 fold in all patients expect in pancreatic necrosis where serum lipase raise in 5 fold. All the patients were investigated to find out complication (systemic/ local)
- Systemic complications were diagnosed by routine blood investigation, RFT, LFT, serum calcium, serum lipase, serum amylase and chest X ray. Local complications were diagnosed by USG abdomen and CT scan. 27 patients found

to have systemic complications and 23 local complications.

- Most systemic complications were managed in general wards except few patients in ICU those were associated with septicemia and ARDS. Systemic complications were managed with supportive and conservative management.
- Local complications were managed conservatively and with operative procedures. Pseudocyst <6 cm were managed with regular USG abdomen follow up 75% resolved Pseudocyst >6 cm undergone operative procedure.
- All the patients with pancreatic necrosis were kept in ICU. Sterile necrosis was managed by supportive and conservative therapy for average 3 weeks. 80% recovered well 20% died due to secondary infection and septicemia. Sterile necrosis was managed with necrosectomy + closed drain with mortality rate of 33%. Pancreatic abscess were managed by USG/CT guided aspiration.

Statistical Analysis: The collected data was summarized by using frequency, percentage, mean & S.D. To compare the qualitative outcome measures Chi-square test or Fisher's exact test was used. To compare the quantitative outcome measures independent t test was used. If data was not following normal distribution, Mann Whitney U test was used. SPSS version 22 software was used to analyse the collected data. p value of <0.05 was significant.

Discussion

The burden of AP is only expected to increase over time. Despite recent advances in medicine, pancreatitis continues to be associated with a substantial morbidity and mortality. The most common cause of AP is gallstones, followed closely by alcohol use. The diagnosis of pancreatitis is established with any two of three following criteria: (1) Abdominal pain consistent with that of AP; (2) Serum amylase and/or lipase greater than three times the upper limit of normal; and (3) Characteristic findings seen in cross-sectional abdominal imaging. Multiple criteria and scoring systems have been established for assessing severity of AP. The cornerstones of management include aggressive intravenous hydration, appropriate nutrition, and pain management. Several randomized controlled trials and cohort studies have recently highlighted the advantage of managing these conditions with a progressive approach, with initial draining for infection followed by less invasive techniques.

Hines OJ et al have studied recent guidelines on management of severe acute pancreatitis. The risks, measurements of severity, and management of severe acute pancreatitis and its complications have

evolved rapidly over the past decade. Evidence suggests that initial goal directed therapy, nutritional support, and vigilance for pancreatic complications are best practice. Patients can develop pancreatic fluid collections including acute pancreatic fluid collections, pancreatic pseudocysts, acute necrotic collections, and walled-off necrosis. Several randomized controlled trials and cohort studies have recently highlighted the advantage of managing these conditions with a progressive approach, with initial draining for infection followed by less invasive techniques. Surgery is no longer an early intervention and may not be needed. Instead, interventional radiologic and endoscopic methods seem to be safer with at least as good survival outcomes. Newly developed evidence-based quality indicators are available to assess and improve performance. Development and clinical testing of drugs to target the mechanisms of disease are necessary for further advancements. [4]

Karakayali FY et al evaluated surgical and interventional management of complications caused by acute pancreatitis. In severe cases there is persistent organ failure and a mortality rate of 15% to 30%, whereas mortality of mild pancreatitis is only 0% to 1%. Treatment principles of necrotizing pancreatitis and the role of surgery are still controversial. Despite surgery being effective for infected pancreatic necrosis, it carries the risk of long-term endocrine and exocrine deficiency and a morbidity and mortality rate of between 10% to 40%. Considering high morbidity and mortality rates of operative necrosectomy, minimally invasive strategies are being explored by gastrointestinal surgeons, radiologists, and gastroenterologists. Since 1999, several other minimally invasive surgical, endoscopic, and radiologic approaches to drain and debride pancreatic necrosis have been described. In patients who do not improve after technically adequate drainage, necrosectomy should be performed. [5] When minimal invasive management is unsuccessful or necrosis has spread to locations not accessible by endoscopy, open abdominal surgery is recommended. Additionally, surgery is recognized as a major determinant of outcomes for acute pancreatitis, and there is general agreement that patients should undergo surgery in the late phase of the disease. It is important to consider multidisciplinary management, considering the clinical situation and the comorbidity of the patient, as well as the surgeons experience.

Zerem E studied that severe acute pancreatitis (SAP), which is the most serious type of this disorder, is associated with high morbidity and mortality. SAP runs a biphasic course. During the first 1-2 wk, a pro-inflammatory response results in systemic inflammatory response syndrome (SIRS). If the SIRS is severe, it can lead to early multisystem

organ failure (MOF). After the first 1-2 wk, a transition from a pro-inflammatory response to an anti-inflammatory response occurs; during this transition, the patient is at risk for intestinal flora translocation and the development of secondary infection of the necrotic tissue, which can result in sepsis and late MOF. Many recommendations have been made regarding SAP management and its complications. However, despite the reduction in overall mortality in the last decade, SAP is still associated with high mortality. In the majority of cases, sterile necrosis should be managed conservatively, whereas in infected necrotizing pancreatitis, the infected non-vital solid tissue should be removed to control the sepsis. Intervention should be delayed for as long as possible to allow better demarcation and liquefaction of the necrosis. Currently, the step-up approach (delay, drain, and debride) may be considered as the reference standard intervention for this disorder.

Conclusion

Management of complicated pancreatitis consists of supportive care and conservative management for systemic complications. Local complications are managed by conservative as well as operative procedure. Most pseudocyst < 6 cm size are managed by USG abdomen follow up and pseudocyst >6 cm requires operative intervention in the form of cystogastrostomy or percutaneous drainage. Pancreatic necrosis is managed by necrosectomy+ close drain. Abscesses were

managed by USG/CT guided aspiration. Pancreatic ascites and pleural effusion are managed by repeated pleural tap and ascetic tap respectively. In general mortality from local complications was 13% mortality from systemic complication was 4%.

Declarations:

Funding: None **Conflicts of interest/Competing interests:** None **Availability of data and material:** Department of Surgery MMIMSR, Mullana, Ambala **Code availability:** Not applicable **Consent to participate:** Consent taken **Ethical Consideration:** There are no ethical conflicts related to this study. **Consent for publication:** Consent taken

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